

Information System Analysis and Design Article (September 2021)

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Abstract—The development of technology in the current era of globalization is accelerating very rapidly and information is circulating more and more complex so that the world of education must be able to follow technological developments, especially in the field of computer technology, along with the development of technology today. The human need for information at this time becomes so easily met with the presence of the internet, which allows the transfer of information only by a matter of second. Development of this globalization era has made everyone in this world must know about the system information. Every single website in the internet, phones, even smartwatch had a view and that design with teh system information technice and language. So, it said the information system analysis and design became a important thing in the world. The processes to made the world know about the information system analysis and design is not easy. It takes so many times to development, but it takes more time to share with public. So many aspect that could be discuss, but on this paper the discussion topic just to introduce what the information system and analysis. Method that writer do in this paper read and made a conclusion related to the material that had relationship with information sistem analysis and design.

Key Word : Information System, Analysis, Design, and Internet

I. INTRODUCTION

The development of information systems is now very fast and rapid, not a few who use information systems to help ease of work. One form of information system easy to develop is web-based, web-based information systems not only is it used to display information, but it can used to dialogue with data so as to provide information to make a decision.

Information sistem is a design result of human and it consist of many component on an organization to achive the goal, and the goal is to serve the useful information for public^[1].The information system had become a communicative information with every component that could made the reader of the people that accept the information satisfy. For example the designer of a wedding dress did not want their client complaint and difficulty with their dress. As same as the wedding dress, the analysis and designer of information system didnt want to got a bad review for their art and complaining with their message of information. The era had became so complex until the destination object can promote on the internet even the train,plane, and planning to detination had arranged^[2].

The information system had a many definition on progress to development the every aspect that become the object. Like website, application, market place and so on. The definition of information system divided by the word that build them. Information is the processed data becomes more useful and meaningful for the recipient, as well as to reduce uncertainty in decision making and for the system is gathering people that working together to achieve the same goal, with some kind of sistematic rules to made union and didnt make a contradiction each other. Other than that information system can helped humanity. The case on this world was very variety like disability person. Information system could be helping them to talk with every single person, it means the information system just not to helping financial section but every section in this world^[3].

Information system has a meaning why this rhing became important for got the goal. Information system must be support the business strategy. If information system didnt have relationship with the business strategy, so it made the process of business didnt increase. The business strategy had to made the information system became other main aspect to develop the process. The good information system of an organization will help the organization to got the client or offer and made business increase as fast as the information system growing.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

On this paper, writer got five literatur which is a journal on JOSI (Jurnal Optimasi Sistem Indutri. The first the literatur that writer got is about the design of quality in the laboratorium of a company. The company made the information system with the spreadsheet to evaluate their experiment in laboratorium to making decision. Other than that the information system have function to archive the data from the past and if sometime needed again they just find in the system. It made the more easy to evaluating what must they improve and refine to got the best oppportunity on their company.

Other literature had discussed about the information system to share or to promote one of island in West Sumatra. They made a design of information system as a web mobile. So if the visitors want to find the tourist attraction,they can found the island. It made the destinations more easy to know, and it reach very wide coverage. Also this information system had a business reasen, because the promoting with the web mobile internet so many visitor came to the island. It made economic

wheel on that place turning. The indigenous sold their art or food or services and made the basic income or passive income. Besides that help visitor easy to find destinations and made profit to our country.

The third literature that writer got is about to manage the inventory of a company. The company is a ground shipping service. So they must have a good appearance for the database and for the way or map to made easier shipping and push the cost until the minimize. The information system became so important on this company section, because it help to made decision of so many choice like where this product more efficient to hold, how the courier can chose the near way on shipping process, and to know and have the data of what them shipping. So, information system became a critical aspect to this business progres. If a mistake happen on the information system, it will make a big problem for company running.

The fourth, literature that writer got was about how the information system became a tool to helping disability person more easy to talk with other people. So many people in this world and some of them had a deficiency on that physics or mental. The literature writer concern about that and made some of tool to help the people with disability a helping gaded to talk with other people. The tool like an application with every image that can made the disability person easier to talk with other people. From this paper we know that the information system didnt just to develop business or company project, but could be a tool to have humanity like this. Imagine if every disability person in this world can used the application, it may us as a person know what them want and made our life better for the future.

And the last literature that writer got on JOSI is about how a company made a better database and analysis of the material requirement planning on them company. It helped company so much because the material requirement planning was a complex tool. If just one or two person understand the good material requirement planning, it will make the company difficult when the unexpected moment. So the role of information system on this problem became a tool to copy the good look and made more staff understand how to fulfill the sheet that had made before.

III. DISCUSSION

The globalization era demanded us to made every information could see for other people on the other region. Like the example when this pandemic era, the manager can stay at China but the factory on the Spain. The manufacturing industry organization is not separated from this. An effective and properly implemented information system will affect the performance of management in controlling the production system of the manufacturing industry^[4]. The information system became an importan thing on every aspect on our life because of that we must discuss about something that had relationship with that.

The definiton of information system is different for the other people depend on what the point that them saw when them made the information system. Writer identify the information system as a tool with every function like helping

people, maximize profit for company and business and other, the tool had relationship with how technology making information became so communicative and interesting.

The function of information system on specific area was so many. So the writer made a general function of information sistem. Example, first is to increase the accebility of the data as efficient and effective to user without third person for example like on the material requirement planning before. the second is to increase productifity development application and maintainance system. in the situation of shipping service is very hard and important because of thar information system became a solution of this poble^[5]. Third is to guarantee the quality because many person believe that something wrote on the internet was a trusted source like journal, article and so on. Fourth is to identify what the market need or we can say a media of survey to know what people on this word want. Fifth is to help a affair of financial and business for a company and organization. The last is to help everyone, organization to manage the data that them have.

Information system had some componet to build a thing view and interaction between the user and system. the component help us to more understand how the information system works. The first component is input component, example when you fulfill the information system on material requirement planning before, you put the number of how much factory can hold our material that is the input component. Then it is the model component. This component containing codes that make our information system work like the calculator that we have. It otomaticly doing what we want like adding number with number, the adding proces on the brain of calculator is model component. The third is output component. It is clearly like the result of calculator that we talk before. The last is technology component, as we know the information system work on technology system like website, phones, application, etc. It is clearly it will have a hardware and software to running the process.

Information system had the characteristic to know it is information system or not. The writer identify some characteristics that can be. The first is new. The information that user can got or used is a fresh information. Second is adding, the information that were on the information system can be adding and if new fact revealed it change or add the last fact. The third is communicative, it means user can use or get information clearly. And the last it can be feedback to the user. The information system must had the output from the what user want.

IV. CONCLUSION

The conclusion of this paper is information system was tool to help people to recognize and manage data with view that can be communicative and accepted to the user that using the information system. Besides of that the information system have so many function like helping disability people, made a company more profit, manage company business and so on. In this era information system became one of king that made this world running, we can do anything with the information system especially on communication section.

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